

PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY NATIONAL FORMATION OF VALUES

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ANNOTATION From time immemorial, the Uzbek people have taught children in their families that the family is a sacred place, that it is necessary to have qualities such as a sense of dignity, duty and responsibility, honesty and truthfulness, respect for elders, and respect for children. sent as an admonition. This article talks about the methods and ways of forming national values in children in the family. In the article, the importance of studying our national and religious values, their essence, their preservation, the invaluable heritage of our ancestors who made a great contribution to the development of world science and culture, on the basis of which, educating young people as perfect human beings will create a stable social and spiritual environment in society. It is said that it is one of the important conditions of provision.

Key words: folklore, national values, proverbs, sayings, riddles, education, national and religious values, Islamic civilization, human perfection, examples of hadith, great scholars, spiritual heritage, oriental education and training.

Today, the loyalty and respect for national and universal values among our people is developing day by day, becoming a source of strength for strengthening the spiritual and moral foundations of independent Uzbekistan, and today, Uzbekistan's independence and prospects, its great future, are placed in the world civilization. The whole world appreciates and recognizes his contribution. Universal human values take a deep place in the heart of every human being, not only in our Republic, but in the whole world as a whole. Preserving our centuries-old national and religious values, we have heard in the stories and advices of our

ancestors, grandmothers. Studying the priceless heritage of our ancestors who made a great contribution to the development of world science and culture, and on the basis of it, educating young people as perfect human beings in society. is one of the important conditions for ensuring a stable socio-spiritual environment. The Center of Islamic Civilization, Islamic Academy, Mir Arab Higher Madrasah, Imam Bukhari and Imam Termizi International Research Centers established in our country in recent years serve to study and promote our rich scientific and historical heritage. At the same time, the analysis of events and socio-political situation in the world requires increasing the effectiveness of activities in the religious and educational sphere and creating a comprehensive system of training qualified personnel. Wide promotion of our noble qualities and values, such as enlightenment, tolerance, kindness, creativity, characteristic of our people since time immemorial, support of representatives of the religious and educational sphere in ensuring the stability of the social and spiritual environment in the society. It is an important task to increase participation and education of the young generation in accordance with our national moral values, to form human qualities in their minds based on the lessons of the science of Hadith, and to instill in them concepts such as patriotism. Values that ensure the existence of man and society are national education due to this, it is gradually passed from ancestors to generations. National education the term is used in broad and narrow senses. In a broad sense, it is a human personality formation, active in its production and social, cultural, educational life all spiritual influences, activities, actions aimed at ensuring participation, means the sum of aspirations. National education in this understanding. only family not educational work carried out in schools, children's and youth organizations, but the entire social system, its leading ideas, literature, art, cinema, radio, It includes TV, media and others. Also, national education in a broad sense includes education and information in this field. In a narrow sense, national education means a pedagogical activity aimed at cultivating the spiritual development, worldview, moral image, and aesthetic taste of a particular person.

This is done by family and educational institutions and public organizations. The most important of the methods promoted in the national values of the Uzbek people are the methods of encouragement and condemnation. In addition, the method of persuasion was also used in the national values of the Uzbek people. Within the framework of the cooperation system of the family-neighborhood preschool education organization, the spiritual and moral education of children through national values was based on the following principles: inheritance, the possession of certain traditions of the dynasty, the age of children, the gender of children and their unique psychological qualities, individual upbringing and creative approach, mother's pedagogical ability, example, respect for national moral values. Great attention should be paid to filling them with Uzbek folk tales, riddles, proverbs and sayings that help them learn about moral qualities - generosity, hard work, justice, peace-loving. . These are mother's tricks, games - entertainment with children ("Claps", "Hand movements", "Imitations of animal movements"), proverbs, proverbs, riddles, fairy tales. Folk art creates great opportunities for the development of children's cognitive activity, independence, individuality, emotions, attitude to the environment, and speech skills. The purposeful and systematic use of various forms of folk art in the spiritual and moral education of children in the pre-school educational institution and in the family lays the groundwork for their spiritual and physical development. Above in the preschool education organization and educational process in the neighborhoods implementation of the noted organizational and pedagogical-psychological conditions in the spiritual and moral upbringing of children with the help of alla, the skills of using alla as a means of education in adolescent girls and young mothers allows to develop formation and methodical preparation. A pedagogical-organizational structure of the process of spiritual and moral upbringing of children in the family with the help of national values was developed. The mechanism of organization and conduct of spiritual and moral events by means of alla in cooperation of family-neighborhood-preschool educational organization is visual-

active thinking, synchronous effect of alla (phonemic sounds) and alla, proverbs, riddles of folk oral creation. , improved based on giving priority to sub-genres such as matal, fast telling, fairy tale. Before talking about the national mentality of the Uzbek people, it should be emphasized that the Uzbek people have experienced 4 major religious and ideological stages {Zoroastrianism, Buddhism, Islam, Communist} and It should not be forgotten how many generations passed before the end of the era of ideological and religious influences and how these processes left an indelible mark on the character of the nation. National customs and traditions are considered important sources of education. by instilling in their minds, in addition to forming spiritual and moral qualities in them, they will be able to deeply understand and respect our national values and, most importantly, apply these values in their daily lives and activities. We have a tradition in it. For example: Every Uzbek family has a ceremony to celebrate the birth of a child, ``suyinchi", cradling the baby, cradle wedding, circumcision.wedding, marriage ceremony, bride's birth, etc. These are just a few features of children's education in the context of our traditions and customs.

Traditions: cradle wedding, circumcision wedding, Muchal wedding, Nigoh wedding, Prophet's wedding, Nowruz holiday, Khosil holiday, Flower holiday, Eids, national games and khakozos.

Traditions - taking a pillow, making a cradle, wearing white, greeting the bride, singing lapar, goat gatekeeper, wrestling, lazy wife, sumalak, making halim and hok. National traditions, customs - getting news from the elderly, beautifying the neighborhood, meeting with an exemplary family, advice from parents, do you know the history of the neighborhood, Navruz, exemplary girls, mushoira, muchal wedding, neighborhood wrestler. , culture, enlightenment, historical memory, national, spiritual value, national language, tradition, custom, these are the most important factors that show the identity of the nation. In general, spiritual heritage, national values It is the embodied expression of the human intellect that has been formed over long periods of spiritual development. Every nation has its own

national values and spiritual heritage that have passed through a long historical period.

In conclusion, I can say that the Uzbek nation has always been an example to other peoples for their rich national past and for raising children. Preserving our centuries-old national and religious values, we have heard in the stories and advices of our ancestors, grandmothers. Studying the priceless heritage of our ancestors who made a great contribution to the development of world science and culture, and on the basis of it, educating young people as perfect human beings in society. I believe that it is one of the important conditions for ensuring a stable socio-spiritual environment.

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